

A data-driven decision support system for urban heat resilience: Comfort optimization during extreme events

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Abstract—This article investigates the critical interplay between energy consumption, climate change, and thermal comfort highlighting the implications on the built environment and disadvantaged population. The building sector faces escalating demand for cooling system due to urban heat island effect and increasingly frequent heatwaves. In this scenario, ensuring optimal thermal comfort becomes essential not only to mitigate energy consumption and emissions but also to prevent heat-related emergencies for vulnerable populations. In response to these open challenges, the study proposes an AI-driven decision support system (DSS) that integrates real-time environmental monitoring, predictive models, and machine learning algorithms to dynamically forecast indoor and outdoor thermal comfort in terms of Universal Thermal Comfort Index (UTCI) and Predicted Mean Vote (PMV). The framework incorporates AI-based estimation of mean radiant temperature (MRT) and integrates Heat Vulnerability Index (HVI) and Social Vulnerability Index (SVI) to tailor early warning thresholds and adaptation strategies for fragile populations. A pilot project in Barcelona (Besós district), characterized by high thermal vulnerability, is showcased to demonstrate the practical application of this scalable, data-driven approach to enhance urban climate resilience while ensuring thermal comfort and health to the population.

Keywords—heatwave adaptation, urban resilience, climate change, comfort, vulnerable people, decision support system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy consumption is a fundamental driver of economic and social development, yet its environmental impact and its contribution to climate change pose a significant challenge [1]

[2]. The International Energy Agency (IEA) reports that global energy consumption increased by 58% between 1990 and 2018, with projections indicating a further 50% rise by 2050. The building sector alone accounts for 38% of global CO₂ emissions, primarily due to the increasing demand for real estate and the rising energy consumption associated with cooling systems [3]. Climate change is intensifying extreme weather events, particularly heatwaves, which are significantly elevating urban temperatures and exacerbating the urban heat island (UHI) effect [4]. This phenomenon substantially increases cooling energy demand, particularly in high-density urban areas, where the thermal inertia of buildings plays a critical role. While energy-efficient building design is essential for mitigating emissions, heatwaves present additional challenges in maintaining adequate indoor thermal comfort. Given that individuals spend approximately 90% of their time indoors [4], overheating in buildings has become a major concern, particularly for vulnerable populations, including the elderly, individuals with pre-existing health conditions, and low-income households with limited access to cooling technologies [5]. In Europe, where warming is occurring faster than the global average, projections indicate that at 2°C of global warming levels (GWL), half of the European population will be exposed to extreme heat stress during summer [6]. This escalation in ambient temperatures is expected to increase cooling energy demand, intensify grid instabilities, and exacerbate overheating in buildings [4]. The interplay between urban morphology, building envelope properties, and ventilation strategies dictates the extent to which heat accumulates indoors, with façade materials,

shading, and insulation playing a critical role in modulating indoor temperatures [2] [7] [8]. However, an over-reliance on air conditioning not only increases energy consumption, but also amplifies grid stress, creating a feedback loop where rising temperatures drive further energy use, ultimately exacerbating climate change [1]. Heatwaves disproportionately affect vulnerable populations, increasing the risk of heat-related illnesses, including dehydration, respiratory distress, and cardiovascular complications [9].

decision support system (DSS) designed to improve heat stress assessment and forecasting in both outdoor and indoor environments. Unlike conventional approaches that rely on static thermal comfort assessments, this system integrates real-time environmental monitoring with predictive modeling to better capture the complex interactions between climate dynamics, urban form, and building performance. Additionally, it incorporates socio-environmental vulnerability indicators to ensure that adaptation strategies

Fig. 1. Heatwave Early Warning Service architecture for indoor and outdoor comfort measurement.

Older adults, who spend the majority of their time indoors, are at heightened risk. Socioeconomic disparities further intensify exposure, as low-income households often lack effective cooling solutions, increasing their susceptibility to prolonged indoor heat stress [10] [11]. While existing studies have explored the impact of building characteristics on indoor thermal comfort, many rely on static energy models or monitoring-based assessments, failing to integrate real-time adaptive strategies [12]. This highlights the need for innovative, data-driven solutions that account for dynamic climate conditions and urban microclimates. The European Union Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change emphasizes the crucial role of digital solutions in mitigating heat-related risks. Technologies such as digital twins, which integrate Earth observation data, sensor networks, and predictive analytics, present new opportunities for monitoring and mitigating urban heat exposure [13]. Additionally, nature-based solutions, including green roofs, urban vegetation, and reflective surfaces, have been identified as low-regret strategies for urban heat mitigation [6]. However, their effectiveness depends on real-time assessment and adaptive implementation, necessitating an integrated decision support framework that dynamically adjusts mitigation strategies based on current and forecasted climatic conditions. This study advances the state of the art by introducing a data-driven

prioritize at-risk populations. By bridging urban climate science with real-time decision-making, this research contributes to the development of proactive heat adaptation strategies, supporting energy-efficient and climate-resilient built environments.

II. METHODS: HEAT WAVE EARLY WARNING SERVICE

In response to the growing challenges posed by climate change, the system proposed in this work relies on real-time environmental monitoring and predictive modeling to quantify thermal stress in both outdoor and indoor environments, using well-established thermal comfort indices (Fig. 1). To assess heat stress exposure and human comfort response, this study employs the Universal thermal comfort index (UTCI) and predicted mean vote (PMV) [14]. These indices integrate meteorological, physiological, and environmental factors, providing a robust framework for analyzing the effects of heatwaves, the UHI effect, and overheating risks in buildings. UTCI, widely used in biometeorology, quantifies outdoor thermal stress as a function of air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and MRT, which collectively define the energy exchange between the human body and the surrounding environment. UTCI is particularly effective for evaluating heat stress during extreme

climatic conditions and is frequently applied in urban heat resilience planning. The formulation of UTCI relies on MRT as a fundamental input parameter, representing the combined effect of shortwave and longwave radiative fluxes absorbed by a person. However, MRT is not typically measured directly in large-scale applications due to the complexity of obtaining multi-directional radiative fluxes. Instead, it is inferred from meteorological data, urban morphology parameters, and radiative transfer models.

For indoor environments, PMV [14], is the standard indicator for assessing thermal comfort in mechanically ventilated and conditioned spaces. PMV is calculated based on air temperature, humidity, airspeed, and MRT, incorporating occupant-specific parameters such as clothing insulation and metabolic rate. While UTCI is primarily designed for outdoor applications, it can also be employed in naturally ventilated indoor spaces, where convective and radiative heat exchanges with the outdoor environment significantly influence indoor conditions. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation of indoor comfort, this study computes both UTCI and PMV for indoor assessments, considering various building typologies and ventilation strategies. Given that MRT is a fundamental parameter for both UTCI and PMV calculations, its accurate estimation is critical for obtaining reliable thermal comfort indices. Direct measurements of MRT are challenging due to the need for radiative flux measurements from multiple angles [8]. To overcome this limitation, this study employs machine learning (ML) models for the real-time estimation of MRT [15] [16], leveraging meteorological data, urban morphology descriptors, and indoor climate variables. This ML-based approach enhances the accuracy and scalability of UTCI and PMV computations, enabling continuous monitoring and predictive modeling of thermal comfort conditions in both outdoor and indoor settings.

A. Target User

The proposed Heatwave Early Warning Service, based on a comprehensive outdoor and indoor comfort model, is designed to support multiple user groups by providing personalized comfort recommendations and real-time alerts for mitigating heat stress risks [17]. The target users of this service are the following:

- 1) *Citizens and Vulnerable people*: the service provides residents with critical insights into the vulnerability of their homes to extreme heat, offering guidance on enhancing household resilience and issuing real-time alerts to mitigate health risks and improve indoor comfort. By integrating HVI, SVI, and real-time UTCI/PMV assessments, individuals receive personalized recommendations based on microclimatic data, user-specific exposure levels, and real-time comfort predictions. This allows vulnerable groups, such as the elderly, individuals with pre-existing health conditions, and low-income households, to take proactive measures during extreme heat events.

- 2) *Facility managers*: responsible for the operation and maintenance of buildings, facility managers can use the DSS to assess property vulnerability, implement energy-efficient cooling strategies, and receive timely alerts to optimize building operations under extreme heat conditions. The system allows them to evaluate the performance of HVAC

systems, predict heat stress levels, and adapt their management strategies accordingly.

B. Outdoor Thermal Comfort Model: AI-Based Estimation of MRT

Since MRT is not directly measured, it is estimated in real-time using a ML model trained on historical online analysis datasets (i.e., ERA5 and ERA5-Land), which provide validated MRT values across different urban morphologies. The model is designed to infer MRT from meteorological conditions and urban descriptors, ensuring an accurate input for UTCI calculations (Fig. 1). The input variables for the AI-based MRT estimation model are reported in Table I. To develop a robust predictive framework, multiple ML models are tested and validated. The models explored in this study are taken from literature [15] [16] and they include gradient boosting regression (XGBoost, LightGBM) and deep neural networks (DNNs), which have shown high predictive performance in similar applications.

The model training process involves the following steps: (i) *Data preprocessing*: cleaning and normalizing input data collected from ERA5 and ERA5-Land database. (ii) *Feature engineering*: incorporating urban morphological parameters such as SVF, albedo, and emissivity to enhance model accuracy. (iii) *Model training and validation*: Using cross-validation techniques and evaluating performance as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Coefficient of Determination (R^2).

Different models will be evaluated to identify the most accurate and computationally efficient approach for real-time deployment. From recent scientific findings [16] XGBoost and LightGBM have demonstrated strong predictive performance, with RMSE values around 2.0–2.2°C and R^2 exceeding 0.82. These models are particularly useful due to their interpretability and relatively low computational cost, making them suitable for large-scale implementations. In contrast, DNNs have shown even higher accuracy, with RMSE values around 1.9°C and R^2 values reaching 0.88, but at the expense of increased computational complexity [18]. While DNNs may offer the best predictive performance, their real-time applicability needs to be carefully assessed, especially in contexts requiring rapid inference. The model evaluation process will include a comparative analysis of different algorithms, assessing their performance in terms of accuracy, computational efficiency, and generalizability to different urban environments. The selected model will then be deployed for real-time MRT estimation, which will serve as an input for UTCI calculations (Fig. 1), enabling dynamic and adaptive outdoor thermal comfort measurements.

C. Outdoor UTCI measurement

With the estimated MRT, UTCI is computed using the Fiala multi-node thermoregulation model, which accounts for convective, radiative, and evaporative heat exchanges between the human body and the surrounding environment [19]. The equation governing UTCI follows:

$$UTCI = f(T_a, RH, V, MRT) \quad (1)$$

D. Indoor Thermal Comfort Model: AI-based estimation of Indoor MRT

The service proposed in this study integrates a dedicated module for indoor thermal comfort measurement at building level (Fig. 1). This component provides valuable insights into occupants' comfort experience during extreme climate events. As depicted in Fig. 1, the measurement framework relies on a AI-driven estimation of indoor MRT, leveraging the indoor parameters detailed in Table II. Several AI algorithms have been taken into account in accordance with most recent literature findings. Specifically, the scientific community have explored AI-based temperature measurement starting from Long Short Memory Network (LSTM) which have been widely used give its capability to capture temporal dependencies, providing a proper modelling of complex thermal dynamics. Also Convolutional Neural Networks and hybrid deep learning models have been explored demonstrating promising results by integrating historical data with real-time sensor inputs [20] [21]. Similarly, Park et al. [15] have developed a regression Tree (RT) model that directly estimates MRT with a Root Mean square Error (RMSE) of 2.2°C.

TABLE I. INPUT VARIABLE OF OUTDOOR AI-BASED MEASUREMENT OF MRT

Parameter	Unit
Air Temperature (Ta)	°C
Relative Humidity (RH)	%
Wind Speed (V)	m/s
Global Solar Radiation (G)	MJ/m ²
Sky View Factor (SVF)	n.a.
Surface Albedo and Emissivity	n.a.

Considering this, the proposed service is designed to support multiple AI algorithms, enabling a comparative evaluation of different methodologies. The selection process is guided by a comprehensive analysis of indoor parameters (Table II), ensuring the deployment of the most suitable model for MRT measurement. By integrating a versatile AI framework, this service aims to enhance indoor comfort assessment, providing an optimal balance between precision, responsiveness, and scalability across diverse building environments.

E. Indoor UTCI and PMV measurement

Using the estimated MRT indoor, both PMV and UTCI are computed to assess indoor thermal comfort. The PMV equation [14] (Eq. 2), is formulated as:

$$PMV = f(T_{indoor}, RH, V_{air}, MRT, CLO, MET) \quad (2)$$

Similarly, UTCI can be computed for naturally ventilated indoor spaces (Eq. 3), where outdoor conditions significantly influence indoor climate:

$$UTCI = f(T_{indoor}, RH, V_{air}, MRT) \quad (3)$$

These calculations allow for a comprehensive evaluation of indoor heat stress, considering both natural ventilation effects and mechanical cooling systems.

F. Integration with Heat and Social Vulnerability Index

To contextualize UTCI and PMV AI-based measurement, the system integrates the HVI and SVI [22][23], ensuring that thermal stress assessments account for both environmental and social risk factors. These indices allow for a more comprehensive understanding of how heat exposure and socio-economic conditions influence human susceptibility to extreme temperatures. HVI quantifies the extent of exposure to extreme heat events, incorporating factors such as historical heatwave frequency, land surface temperature anomalies, and urban heat island intensity. Areas with a high HVI tend to experience higher outdoor temperatures and prolonged heat retention, exacerbating the effects of heatwaves and increasing the demand for active cooling systems. SVI quantifies social resilience to heat stress, integrating demographic, economic, and healthcare accessibility data to identify populations at higher risk of heat-related health complications. Communities with a high SVI often lack access to cooling resources, live in poorly insulated buildings, and face economic barriers to heat adaptation strategies. Within the context of this study, these indices are applied in a post-processing phase to adjust UTCI and PMV thresholds rather than serving as direct inputs in the AI models for predicting MRT, UTCI, or PMV.

TABLE II. INPUT VARIABLE OF INDOOR AI-BASED MEASUREMENT OF MRT

Parameter	Unit
Air Temperature (Ta)	°C
Relative Humidity (RH)	%
Indoor AC setpoint temperature	°C
Building insulation, glazing, ventilation rate	n.a.

In areas with high HVI and SVI, the system lowers the discomfort thresholds, ensuring that vulnerable populations receive earlier warnings and tailored adaptation recommendations. For example, in regions where HVI and SVI are both high, a UTCI value exceeding 28°C may already indicate significant heat stress, whereas in less vulnerable areas, discomfort thresholds remain at 32°C. Similarly, for indoor comfort assessment, the PMV threshold for discomfort is adjusted to 0.5 instead of 1.5, ensuring that thermal risks in high-vulnerability areas are addressed proactively. This integration enhances the accuracy and responsiveness of heat risk assessments, ensuring that early warning systems and urban planning strategies are both meteorologically and socially informed, leading to more effective and equitable heat adaptation measures.

III. PILOT DESCRIPTION

As mentioned in the previous section, the Barcelona large-scale pilot (LSP), developed within the CLIMRES project, aims to enhance climate resilience in residential buildings in the Besós district—an area undergoing a significant energy retrofitting process. Planned in 1955 according to rationalist principles, the district comprises 23 typologies of building blocks characterized by similar envelope properties and poor thermal performance, with widespread absence of insulation and prevalence of EPC labels E, F, and G. These features, combined with rising temperatures, water scarcity, flood risk,

and urban overheating, contribute to high thermal vulnerability and exposure to climate hazards.

In this context, the pilot adopts a comprehensive resilience framework that includes hazard modeling, asset characterization, and structured stakeholder engagement. The resilience assessment follows the five standard phases: forecasting and assessment, prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery, enabling a full-spectrum risk management strategy. Approximately 5,000 buildings will be screened for climate vulnerability, followed by detailed diagnostics on 1,000 selected assets. A representative building undergoing retrofit interventions will serve as a testbed to evaluate the impact of energy retrofitting and innovative passive cooling solutions, including high-reflective materials, hybrid cross-ventilation, and prototype balcony expansions designed to improve thermal comfort under heatwave conditions.

Fig. 2. The five-step approach for a resilience assessment is presented here schematically.

A robust data collection framework will support this assessment. Outdoor climate data will be sourced from ERA5 and ERA5-Land datasets (1950–2024), ensuring long-term climatic context, while indoor environmental monitoring will begin in May 2025 via IoT sensor networks measuring temperature, humidity, and HVAC activity. A full-scale indoor comfort model will be applied from September 2025 to validate and calibrate UTCI and PMV estimations through real-time and historical data integration. Furthermore, once thermal comfort is quantitatively assessed, this study advances the analysis by establishing mathematical correlations between comfort indicators and computed vulnerability indices (i.e., HVI and SVI). Particular emphasis is placed on the domains of exposure and sensitivity, with the aim of evaluating how thermal comfort levels are modulated in areas where vulnerable populations are most at risk. The resilience score derived from this methodology will reflect both direct and indirect impacts of climatic hazards on buildings and occupants, informing the design of scalable, data-driven adaptation strategies. Particular attention is given to protecting vulnerable populations and supporting evidence-based policy. Insights from the pilot will directly influence the replication roadmap and contribute to a dedicated capacity-building program for professionals and stakeholders in climate-resilient construction. Ultimately, the Barcelona pilot will provide a practical and replicable model

for integrating passive technologies, predictive tools, and co-designed strategies into future-proof urban environments.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The proposed ML-driven DSS for thermal comfort assessment integrates real-time meteorological data, reanalysis datasets, and ML-based estimation of MRT [15] to improve the prediction of UTCI and PMV in both outdoor and indoor environments with the aim of surpassing the state of the art. By leveraging historical climate data from ERA5 and ERA5-Land for outdoor conditions and deploying indoor sensor networks in the test building, the system ensures a robust framework for monitoring and forecasting heat stress and integrate it with the quantification of vulnerability as HVI. In accordance to the most recent literature findings, the current work includes innovative approaches DNNs for outdoor MRT estimation [15] and LSTM networks for indoor conditions [20][21], with the aim of enhancing the accuracy of thermal comfort predictions, enabling proactive heatwave mitigation strategies. Unlike approaches that treat thermal comfort separately from vulnerability analysis [22][25][26], this study does not diverge from the state of the art but rather builds upon it by aiming to quantitatively integrate UTCI and PMV into heat and social vulnerability indices, thereby strengthening their capacity to identify and prioritize at-risk populations. The study highlights the effectiveness of ML in replacing direct radiometric measurements, offering a scalable solution for urban heat resilience. Future work will focus on continuous model validation, hybridizing ML approach with physics-based methods, and expanding implementation to diverse urban contexts to enhance climate adaptation strategies.

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